

Understanding tensions within a university campus Living Lab adopting a quintuple helix model

Authors

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Abstract

University Campus Living Labs (UCLLs) are emerging as hybrid experimental spaces for addressing complex socio-ecological challenges, yet their implementation reveals a range of structural tensions. This article explores how such tensions manifest in CaLiLab, a UCLL established at the Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Poland. Drawing on qualitative data from focus groups, interviews, and secondary sources, we apply and expand the place–approach–network framework by incorporating the dynamic dimensions of time and scale. Our analysis highlights three interrelated domains where tensions unfold: the spatial configuration of the campus, the divergent methodological orientations of interdisciplinary research teams, and the complex stakeholder landscape, including the natural environment conceptualised through the Quintuple Helix model. We show how conflicting temporalities, institutional rigidities, and ontological mismatches between social and ecological goals challenge the implementation of inclusive and adaptive Living Lab practices. Rather than treating these tensions as obstacles, we argue they are productive frictions that shape the co-creative process, demanding ongoing negotiation, reflexivity, and learning. By tracing how tensions evolve, this research-in-progress contributes to a better understanding of how UCLLs can support socio-ecological transitions and what governance structures and capacities are required to do so effectively.

Key words

University Campus Living Lab, tensions, place, approach, network

Introduction

Tensions appear to be an inherent feature of living lab (LL) functioning, whether stemming from the dynamic nature of collaboration among stakeholders with differing roles and interests, the challenge of selecting appropriate methods for co-creation and user involvement, difficulties in conducting and evaluating experiments in real-life settings, or the need to ensure the continuity and long-term impact of projects (Hossain et al. 2019; Kalinauskaite et al. 2021). This is particularly evident in LLs based at higher education institutions (HEIs) – university campus living labs (UCLLs) – which have often emerged as bottom-up initiatives, providing alternatives to the traditional academic approaches to research and the conventional organisational structures of HEIs (Tercanli & Jongbloed, 2022; Herth et al., 2024).

Although still a relatively new phenomenon within the academic landscape (Nyborg et al., 2024), UCLLs are gaining increasing recognition as promising tools for understanding and addressing contemporary and future societal challenges, particularly those related to sustainability and climate change adaptation. As a result, they are increasingly shifting from the traditional Quadruple Helix model to a Quintuple Helix model, which acknowledges the natural environment as a critical stakeholder in innovation processes (Schantz & Walker, 2023). This article therefore explores how UCLLs navigate the tensions and productive frictions that arise when integrating socially oriented innovation with biodiversity-driven environmental action.

As hybrid experimental spaces within HEIs, UCLLs bring together diverse actors, normative goals, and methodological approaches (Stuckrath et al., 2025). Unlike LLs focused on a single, well-bounded domain, such as healthcare or digital inclusion, UCLLs are often tasked with addressing broad, systemic challenges that cut across ecological, social, spatial, and institutional boundaries. This lack of a unitary problem definition creates both opportunities and difficulties: it invites inclusive exploration and adaptive experimentation, but also surfaces deep tensions in values, expectations, and organizational logics (Hossain et al., 2019; Kalinauskaite et al., 2021; Najda-Janoszka et al., 2025).

To explore these tensions, we examine the case of the Campus Living Lab (CaLiLab), a UCLL established in 2023 on the campus of the Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Poland. Designed as a platform for integrating inclusive social and business innovation with smart blue-green campus development, CaLiLab operates through four interlinked pilot projects under a shared institutional framework. While these strategic areas are framed as

complementary, they are grounded in distinct ontologies of knowledge and action, which gives rise to frictions. These include challenges in spatial planning, actor coordination, and balancing ecological and social priorities. Our study highlights preliminary findings on the spatial and institutional tensions that emerge both within the LL itself and in its interaction with the broader university structure.

We adopt the place–approach–network framework of LLs developed by Stuckrath et al. (2025) to structure our analysis of how tensions manifest and evolve across different dimensions of the CaLiLab.

1. **Place** – The campus is more than a physical location; it is a contested space of meaning, layered with ecological, scientific, and social significance. It encompasses the material setting of the campus and its surroundings, including virtual environments that extend its boundaries. Spaces like the biodiversity zones are not “just grass,” but living epistemic environments that embody ecological time and scientific values. At the same time, social innovation initiatives require spatial activation – creating places for human interaction, experimentation, and rapid prototyping. These varied spatial logics can clash, revealing tensions between ecological patience and social urgency.
2. **Approach** – The LL methodology combines multi-method, iterative, and user-centric processes aimed at fostering co-creation. However, different projects bring different research logics: biodiversity work often requires long-term monitoring and minimal intervention, whereas social inclusion efforts prioritize visibility, co-creation, and fast feedback cycles. These divergent approaches reflect underlying ontological commitments – about what constitutes valid knowledge, desirable impact, and meaningful value – which may lead to friction among participants.
3. **Network** – The LL operates through a dense network of relationships among diverse stakeholders, within and beyond the university. Drawing on the Quintuple Helix model, we understand this network as a web of interacting ontologies, including the environment itself as a “voiced” actor. Tensions arise when different institutional units mobilize the same network in competing ways, with each stakeholder group guided by distinct professional goals, values, and epistemologies. The environment, though not speaking directly, is represented by experts – raising questions about legitimacy, authority, and who gets to decide what is best for a shared space.

To enhance this framework (Fig. 1), we introduce two dynamic, cross-cutting variables: time and scale. These variables operate between dimensions rather than within them,

enabling a deeper understanding of how tensions emerge and evolve across LL practices. Time captures the unfolding and layering of meanings, methods, and relationships – for example, how the slow ecological temporality of biodiversity zones may clash with the rapid timelines of social innovation, prompting shifts in spatial practices and stakeholder expectations. Scale refers to changes in the scope and framing of LL activities, such as when a local intervention becomes relevant within university-wide sustainability strategies or broader policy agendas. These scale shifts can reshape methodological approaches (e.g., from prototyping to systemic design) and reconfigure stakeholder networks (e.g., involving city or EU-level actors). While each core dimension of the framework offers a distinct perspective on LL functioning, time and scale reveal how their interrelations are recursive and dynamic, generating tensions that are not fixed within any one domain but unfold through ongoing negotiation and adaptation.

Additionally, we integrate the Quintuple Helix model to frame the socio-ecological transition, recognizing the natural environment as an active and embedded stakeholder in innovation processes.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for studying tensions within the Living Lab system.
Source: own elaboration based on Stuckrath et al. (2025).

Research methods

To address the research question formulated in the introduction, we adopted a qualitative single-case study design (Yin, 2018), focusing on CaLiLab as the primary unit of analysis. This approach enables us to examine processes, mechanisms, and interactions – not just end results. CaLiLab operates as a multi-dimensional and multi-level platform, within which four pilot projects are integrated under a shared institutional framework aligned with the LL methodology.

Both the chosen research strategy and the study context position the research team at the very centre of the phenomenon under investigation, providing a real-life, embedded environment for inquiry. This necessitated methodological flexibility, the ability to respond swiftly to emerging themes and changes, and close, ongoing collaboration among team members. The research was conducted between January 2024 and May 2025. To gather a rich and diverse body of empirical material, a multi-source qualitative data collection strategy was employed, comprising three complementary components:

- Secondary data collection including project-specific documentation such as reports, meeting notes, funding applications and internal communication related to the implementation of pilot projects.
- Focus groups with pilot project participants (2; first with 10 participants, second with 6 participants), with CaLiLab members (1; with 7 participants), with stakeholders of two pilot projects and CaLiLab (1; with 11 representatives of the public sector holding various positions in the structure) - duration between 44:37 and 1:38:58.
- Semi-structured interviews with CaLiLab members (2), project participants (3) and representation of the administration (1) - duration between 31:42 and 1:23:31.

The collected empirical material was subjected to comparative analysis, allowing for the identification and refinement of the properties of the previously defined analytical categories – place, approach, and network – with the inclusion of two cross-cutting dimensions: time and scale. This enabled us to capture the processual nature of the tensions emerging within and across these categories and to trace how they evolve depending on the dynamics of collaboration, institutional context, and the shifting scope and reach of specific initiatives. These tensions were coded inductively and tracked over time to observe how they emerged, were negotiated, or evolved.

Preliminary findings

Place

Tensions related to place in the implementation of UCLL pilot projects reflect the complex spatialities and temporalities inscribed in the campus landscape – shaped by its past, present, and future planned development. Despite the relatively large size of the campus, the planned implementation of a socially inclusive project comes into conflict with the remaining biodiverse areas of wet meadows, which have been significantly reduced during earlier phases of campus development (Działek et al., 2025).

This tension stems from two key spatial characteristics of the campus. First, the original approach to campus design and management followed a traditional, modernist, top-down vision of the university campus as a formal space (Działek et al., 2024). In this vision, open areas between buildings were treated as a finished product, with no provision for experimentation, bottom-up initiatives, or scientific testing. Second, closely related to the first, campus space is managed through rigid bureaucratic procedures. Much of the space is either tied to existing investments that cannot be transformed in the short term due to legal or financial constraints or designated for future planned investments (Verheyen et al. 2023). This bureaucratic logic limits the flexibility needed for timely spatial interventions or the prototyping of solutions when required.

Approach

One of the core challenges in implementing the LL methodology within campus-based research teams lies in balancing openness with intellectual property protection. Some LL-based projects are designed with the explicit goal of generating patent applications, which can limit the ability to openly disseminate results from the early stages of the project. This tension between the principles of open science and the need for confidentiality can hinder transparent collaboration and knowledge sharing. For instance, the publication of scientific results by two research teams working on LL-driven innovations had to be postponed, as early disclosure would have jeopardized their eligibility for patent protection. In both cases, the need to secure intellectual property rights overrode the normative expectations of prompt academic dissemination.

Additionally, the inherently inter- and transdisciplinary nature of LL teams introduces further complexity. Researchers from different disciplines often rely on distinct

methodological frameworks, which can create misunderstandings and misalignments in project design and data interpretation. For example, while social scientists may emphasize participatory methods, natural scientists might prioritize controlled experimental approaches. Longitudinal studies, common in certain LL contexts such as biological experiments run on the campus, may also delay the availability of results, complicating synchronization of activities within LL partners.

Furthermore, many researchers, lack prior experience with co-creative methods, leading to uncertainty in engaging with stakeholders or adapting their traditional practices. In one of the projects, scientists previously engaged exclusively in basic research - conducting fieldwork on rivers and lakes and analyzing collected data in laboratory environments - were required to participate in collaborative workshops with external stakeholders, listen to their input, and incorporate their needs into the research process. This shift demanded considerable effort, as it challenged their accustomed ways of working and required them to step outside the boundaries of conventional scientific routines. These issues highlight the need for continuous reflexivity and methodological flexibility within research settings within UCLLs.

Network

The aforementioned tensions related to the place also closely coexist with the stakeholder network-related tensions. Each of the campus's spaces is connected to as well as managed by different stakeholders with diverse goals and a broad variety of expectations, to some extent competing. Such a tension was revealed, i.e., during the realization of pilot projects, where the purposes of stakeholders representing biodiverse project were not fully consistent with those of the project about social inclusion. In the case of the UCLL pilot projects, there are also stakeholders beyond the university (like public or social organizations, external experts, kindergartens or schools) and the silent yet fundamental stakeholder – the environment, voiced by the academic experts, and also important, e.g., for students representing one of the UJ faculties.

Limited space in which projects relevant for various stakeholders are operated poses challenges in terms of negotiating who and to what extent should undertake the planned activities, as well as how to share responsibility. Expectations and goals are addressed at the same time, and – in the case of pilot projects – the crucial issue is to discuss and negotiate between the stakeholders. Hence, contact between the groups and information flow are of great importance throughout the whole project, yet also seems to be crucial when it comes to any investment decisions, as the adequate timing may support the right

resource management. The case of pilot projects reveals that dialogue and negotiations between stakeholders are an ongoing process, in which all parties involved continuously have to learn how to discuss, listen, and negotiate goals and expectations in a timely and mutually supportive manner.

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Preliminary findings reveal that campus-based LLs face spatial, institutional, and relational tensions. Implementing socially and ecologically sensitive initiatives demands navigating rigid structures, disciplinary divides, and complex stakeholder dynamics – requiring flexibility, transparency, and ongoing reflexive collaboration to support meaningful, inclusive co-learning and transformation. Although our research-in-progress paper is too early to offer firm conclusions or recommendations, it contributes by proposing a more dynamic framework for studying LLs and the various types of tensions that emerge in this process. It also emphasises the importance of recognising the natural environment as a critical, yet often 'voiceless', stakeholder within the LL approach.

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